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Collaborative teaching as a tool in university development

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ABSTRACT

Goal of interdisciplinary education is to improve learning of students: to support deep learning and adaptation of working life skills. In this context, teachers are seen as resources at courses. However, interdisciplinary collaborative teaching can also be seen as a tool for teachers' continual learning, implementation of universities' education strategies, and seed when building cross-cutting communities in universities. All these perspectives have emerged in the interdisciplinary co-teaching context in Aalto University. Aalto was borne as a merger of three universities from areas of business, design and technology. Aalto aims at building competitive edge by combining knowledge from different disciplines. Consequently, interdisciplinarity in education must be central in Aalto. In this study, we focus on the course development process practices, which build have been used in development of interdisciplinary education in Aalto: i) pedagogical mentoring, ii) entrepreneurship integration, and iii) interdisciplinary minor program. The attempt of the present study on Aalto experiences is to bring visible the challenges and enablers as well as to make suggestions on best practices.

1 INTRODUCTION

1.1 Need for change in university education

University teaching development incentives stem both from inside universities and from the world outside. The pressure for changes from outside is the ever tighter competition in education field which has made good quality teaching a competitive edge. Universities themselves have own strategic targets for teaching development. For instance, integration of sustainability in teaching according to Sustainable Development Goals Accord is a goal which has been signed by dozens of

universities globally (SDGA 2019). Other example is entrepreneurial mind-set, which has emerged as a central theme in university teaching during last decades and is in special focus area in Aalto University (Aarnio 2019). Furthermore, present study showcases a situation in which a merger of existing universities takes place, and in which the attempt is to enhance interaction between the different units. The combining factor in all three mentioned cases of strategic themes implementation in university education call for interdisciplinary education: Sustainable development deals with wicked problem which combine multiple disciplines, entrepreneurship education builds strongly on multidisciplinary (Aarnio 2019), and finally: the merger of universities from different disciplines (Design, Business, Engineering) must have a goal in increased interdisciplinary collaboration. Notably, the collaboration includes research and education, but in this study we focus in education. Regardless of the source of the initiative to develop interdisciplinary teaching, the actual implementation will take place at courses. This, in turn, calls for teaching development done by teacher(s) at the courses.

1.2 Course development process

Course development can be seen as a continual process with four steps in it. 1) Goal setting stage defines the course goals regarding to students' learning, grades, course feedback and/or pass/fail-ratio. During 2) course planning stage, the resource requirements; spaces, teachers, assistants, prior learning requirement, schedule are defined. Here also the course activities: project work, syllabus, learning assessment tools are decided. 3) Actual course execution, which includes teaching sessions and their detail design, assessment, student information and communication. 4) Course evaluation covers learning assessment and course feedback. The evaluation outcomes feed the goal setting of the next round (Figure 1).

Fig.1 Continual course development process.

1.3 Co-teaching

Co-teaching may be defined as two or more teachers working together according to general definition of co-work. It is not studied in large in university context (Zhou et al. 2011). However, research in general indicates that co-teaching benefits for both teachers and students as summarised by Zhou et al. (2011). While students show for example more motivation, improved teamwork abilities and interdisciplinary learning, teachers will learn from each other's experiences and learning styles.

2 CASE STUDY APPROACH

2.1 Frame

We use the course development process as a framework to analyse the prospects and contradictions when teaching alone or with a multiple teachers (at least two).

2.2 Study material

The present preliminary analysis is based on experiences of teachers who have been involved in different types of teaching. The teachers come from Aaltonaut-program, Teaching partner-course (TP) and Aalto Ventures Program (AVP). They have experience on teaching alone, as teacher in charge at multi-teacher course, and a member of teaching team. The programs have been focusing on interdisciplinary teaching and collaborating with disciplinary courses in order to integrate transferrable competencies and new teaching practises. Teaching partner-course is a mentoring program to enhance development and experimentation in teaching.

2.3 Definitions in the study scope

The actors in the scope, Aaltonaut, AVP, and TP have strived to bring strategic themes in teaching: Aaltonaut interdisciplinarity and working life skills, AVP entrepreneurship and working life skills, and TP pioneering, student centred teaching.

Aaltonaut-program (est. 2013) has been forerunner for interdisciplinary teaching at Bachelor's degree studies in Aalto University. It has functioned as a teaching development platform and all the courses of the program (seven courses) are collaborative teaching courses. The teachers at the program come from different schools of Aalto University and represent different disciplines.

AVP is established (2013) to promote entrepreneurship ecosystem and entrepreneurial mind-set development. AVP has been activist in providing support for teachers in order to integrate entrepreneurial elements in their courses.

TP (est. 2014) is a pedagogical mentoring course which aims at supporting both individual teachers, teaching teams at courses and at study programs to develop teaching by practical experimentations. The program is largely based on research done by Clavert (2018).

All the named actors have perspectives in teaching as a solitary teacher and as a teaching team.

3 RESULTS

The results are presented here in chapters following the course development process stages and summarised in table 1.

3.1 Goals setting

Setting course goals as the only teacher at the course is straightforward as the results from previous round and the course basics are own knowledge. Evidently, there is no need to agree upon goals for the next round in terms of learning outcomes, course feedback, pass/fail ratio and/or other criteria.

When it comes to setting goals jointly, finding a consensus on the goals calls for discussion and agreeing. These goals may iterate and develop during the planning process. Furthermore, feedback from the previous round needs to be documented and accessible for the whole teaching team.

3.2 Planning

Course planning as a solitary teacher may be done according to own schedule with no separate time allocation. The whole picture of the course is in the head of the course teacher and there is no need to fix and agree on course concept, syllabus, emphasis on different areas, or any other topic. Fitting together the course components is straight forward. However, when planning alone, there is no direct need to adapt new approaches, new methods, or new course concepts. Accordingly, the only motivation for planning new teaching experimentations, comes from teacher her/himself. Furthermore, in the case of interdisciplinary course, lack of representative(s) from others discipline(s) reduces the balance between the disciplines. Similarly, when outsourcing e.g. the working life skill teaching to a visiting teacher (without joint planning), the theme may remain unconnected to the course. In both cases: interdisciplinary theme or working life skill integration may remain vague in case of joint planning is missing.

The planning stage becomes more and more laborious along with the increasing number of teachers involved in it. The scheduling of the planning meetings is a whole new activity compared to planning alone. The responsible teacher needs must be clearly named and he/she has to take the responsibility on inviting and planning of the meetings. She/he must balance between making solid plan and keeping the planning open for new approaches. It is very likely that one planning meeting is not enough and more are needed. The roles in planning must be clear concerning who takes care about practicalities such as space reservation, uploading and updating information in course pages, marketing, inviting guests, or organizing excursions. Once agreed course syllabus is more binding as the changes have impact on more than one teacher. The other side of the coin is, that during the planning meeting(s) the teachers learn from each other's experiences and disciplines. This realizes as transfer of course concepts, teaching methods, and best practises. As a

consequence, new developments and plans for experimentations regarding to all these may take place. Furthermore, when teachers learn about each other's disciplines, the connection points between the disciplines become clear for all the parties in the process. Finally, when collaborating in professional context, teachers get to know each other, and in the case of interdisciplinary course, the community exceeds disciplinary and organizational boundaries.

3.3 Execution

When one teacher runs his/her own course there is flexibility in terms of changes during the course. There is no need to discuss or agree on these with others. However, in the case of unexpected changes, such as illness, there is no backup.

In the case of joint execution between two or more teachers, the changes call for communication and agreeing upon. On the other hand, there is possibility to agree and have backup when needed (for instance in case of illness). Furthermore, joint execution enables shared sessions during which students can learn multiple approaches and even debates. Moreover, joint teaching enables and/or facilitates applying various teaching methods: parallel streams of presentations, commenting on teams' work etc. Finally, when it comes to experimentation on a new method, sharing facilitates information gathering as there is possibility for making division into observation and practical execution roles.

3.4 Evaluation

Receiving course feedback and learning results alone is less significant in the case of positive feedback. When it comes to negative feedback, it may feel personal failure instead of potential for learning. Basically, dissemination of the course results is based on teacher's own decision.

When course evaluation is done jointly, the focus is in the course (not in teacher(s) as person(s)). This enables easier transfer of the negative feedback into corrective actions. Specifically, when it comes to new experimentations, the focus in new adaptations and learning instead of discouragement due the feeling of failure is crucial in order to keep on making experimentations.

Table 1. Prospects and contradictions comparison between one and many teachers.

	<i>One teacher</i>	<i>More than one teacher</i>
Goal setting		
Pros	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • <i>Easy to decide</i> • <i>Uniform view on goals</i> 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Multiple perspectives on course goals makes new goal setting more likely.
Cons	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • <i>Hard to renew course goals.</i> • <i>Hard to recognize new approaches.</i> • <i>Limitations in own expertise area may restrict inclusion of transferrable skills in course</i> 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Agreeing on learning goals calls for consensus and discussion and is time consuming.
Planning		
Pros	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • <i>Easy to verify continuation between the sessions.</i> • <i>Easy make adjustments during the course.</i> • <i>Possibility to ask visiting teachers to fill in own gap areas and/or reduce workload.</i> 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Possibility for peer learning on teaching methods and course concepts. • Possible to learn connections between own and other disciplines. • Getting to know teaching personnel from other departments / schools. • Possibility for building teacher community. • Creating visibility for teaching development.
Cons	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Limits the course content near own expertise area. • Interdisciplinary course is challenging to plan from a single perspective 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Scheduling and planning calls for separate effort. • Agreeing on course concept calls for discussion. • Building a logical entity of the course calls for extra effort. Scattered course as a risk if no consensus is found.
Execution		
Pros	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • <i>No gaps in communication during the course.</i> • <i>No need to agree or reschedule adjustments in syllabus.</i> 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Possibility for backup (i.e. in case of illness) • Burden of experimentations is shared. • Co-existence at teaching sessions bring more dialogue and differing approaches in teaching.
Cons	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • <i>No backup (in case of illness)</i> • <i>New experimentations is solely on own solders.</i> • <i>Visiting teachers sessions may remain super imprinted.</i> 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Changes in schedule must be commonly agreed.
Evaluation		
Pros		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Shared feedback easier to focus on course and course development • Shared feedback easier to use in learning.
Cons	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • <i>Feedback is more personal. No sharing of failures or victories.</i> 	

4 SUMMARY

Co-teaching throughout the whole course development process: goal setting, planning, execution, and analysis, is an essential tool when developing interdisciplinary course. Without joint development process different disciplines do not fit together in a well-balanced way. During the development process the teachers get to know different disciplines and the connection points between these and own disciplines. Similarly, co-planning is tool for integration of a new theme in a course, such as entrepreneurship or sustainability. In general, co-teaching enables continual learning, supports teaching experimentations, brings visibility for teaching work, helps in transformation of course feedback into development activity, and build teaching community. In a nutshell, co-teaching is an intermediary for transformation of university teaching.

The other side of the coin is, that co-teaching requires more efforts from all who participate in the teaching, specifically when it comes to course planning and goal setting. Here, co-teaching calls for time allocation for scheduling meetings, planning for meetings, clarification of roles and responsibilities, and communication between the members of the teaching team. Notably, communication is an element, which is not needed in the case of solitary teacher while in the case of multiple teachers, it becomes a central part of the whole course development process. A whole new skill set is needed: On one hand, the teacher in charge of the course needs leadership and managerial skills. On the other hand, the teaching team needs teamwork skill. None of these are traditionally competences, which have been required from teachers.

From the university perspective, co-teaching as a tool for developing teaching to meet the strategic goals, such as integration of sustainability and/or entrepreneurship in education. Furthermore, multidisciplinary teacher community is base for building bridges between the schools and departments of different disciplines. However, in order to utilize the full potential of co-teaching, the challenges related to it must be understood and taken into account. Co-teaching requires support, especially in the beginning. The actual course development can be facilitated by pedagogical mentoring. In general, in order to encourage teachers to put effort in co-teaching, mechanisms to reward the efforts are needed. Rewarding can take place as pedagogical credits or as tenure track proceeding criteria. From organization perspective, incentives are needed for departments and schools which allocate resources for co-teaching. As a conclusion, co-teaching requires resources to produce the sought change in university teaching. Regarding the resource requirement, co-teaching doesn't differ from other teaching development activities, such as pedagogical courses, seminars and workshops on different topics. The difference between co-teaching and the before mentioned activities is that co-teaching impact directly in teaching simultaneously with peer learning and teaching community development.

REFERENCES

Since we are using double-blind reviewing process, also references revealing the identity of the author(s) should be made anonymous until the final paper.

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